

Non-invasive Assessment of Hemodynamic Response of Volume Expansion in Spontaneously Breathing Septic Shock Patients

MoatasemBellah Mohamed, Samir Elhadidy, Mohamed Shehata, RandaSoliman

Critical Care Department, Cairo University, Egypt

Email: manalmanar@mail.com

ABSTRACT

Introduction: The cornerstone of treating patients with septic shock remains as it has been for decades, intravenous fluids. Dosing intravenous fluid during resuscitation of septic shock remains largely empirical. There is now a large body of evidence to show that various dynamic parameters (both invasive and non-invasive) have a high sensitivity and specificity for predicting fluid responsiveness. Large variations in IVC size with IPPV accurately predict fluid responsiveness but its use is still of debate in spontaneously breathing patients.

Objectives: To evaluate the extent to which, respiratory changes in IVC diameter, IVC-collapsibility index (IVC-CI) and left ventricular outflow tract VTI variations can be used to predict fluid responsiveness in septic shock spontaneously breathing not receiving positive mechanical ventilation patients in comparison to static parameters as central venous pressure.

Methods: A total of thirty spontaneously breathing septic shock patients enrolled in our study were subjected to fluid loading of crystalloids 10ml/kg infusion over 15 minutes. All patients were divided into two groups according to fluid responsiveness that defined by an increase in cardiac output 15% or more that measured by transthoracic echocardiography (TTE). Data were collected before and after fluid challenge including mean arterial pressure (MAP), heart rate (HR), central venous pressure (CVP) and oxygen saturation, inferior vena cava collapsibility index (IVCC) by TTE through subcostal window, long axis view, and left ventricular outflow tract VTI by TTE through apical window, 5-chamber view to assess which parameter could reflect fluid status and responsiveness of the patient.

Results: There was no statistical significant difference between fluid responsive and non-responsive group regarding baseline heart rate (p value :0.75), heart rate after volume expansion(p value :0.91),baseline mean arterial blood pressure(p value :0.85), MAP after volume expansion(p value :0.15) , baseline central venous oxygen saturation(p value : 0.28) and saturation after volume expansion (p value : 0.69). It was found that central venous pressure and IVCC have a poor predictive values. Results showed that baseline CVP (AUC:0.59, sensitivity of 55% , specificity of 66%), CVP after volume expansion (AUC:0.52, sensitivity of 50%, specificity of 66%), baseline IVCC (AUC:0.64 sensitivity of 72% specificity of 58%), IVCC after volume expansion(AUC : 0.60 sensitivity of 66% specificity of 75%) and percentage of change of IVCC variations before and after fluid responsiveness (AUC:0.57 sensitivity of 83% specificity of 58%). LVOT VTI variation showed a high predictive values, results showed that baseline VTI (AUC: 0.80 sensitivity of 83% specificity of 83%), VTI after volume expansion (AUC: 0.61 sensitivity of 50% specificity of 83%) and LVOT VTI percentage of change between before and after volume expansion (AUC: 0.92 sensitivity of 94 % specificity of 83 %).

Conclusion: In spite of high predictive value of IVCC to assess fluid responsiveness in mechanically ventilated patients, IVCC and CVP have a poor ability to predict fluid responsiveness in spontaneously breathing septic shock patient. In contrast, LVOT VTI has high predictive values in this type of patients.

Keywords: Septic shock, Fluid responsiveness, IVC collapsibility index, LVOT VTI.

INTRODUCTION

The cornerstone of treating patients with septic shock remains as it has been for decades, intravenous fluids. Surprisingly, dosing intravenous fluid during resuscitation of septic shock remains largely empirical. Too little fluid may result in tissue hypoperfusion and worsen organ dysfunction however, over prescription of fluid also appears to impede oxygen delivery and compromise patient outcome⁽¹⁾.

Cardiac filling pressures also known as static measurements are thought to be a direct reflection of the ventricular pressure and hence the volume of the cardiac chambers. Central venous pressure (CVP) is

the most popular of the static pressures and continues to be recommended in resuscitative protocols and guidelines^(2,3).

How to Cite this Article:

MoatasemBellah Mohamed, Samir Elhadidy, Mohamed Shehata, RandaSoliman(2018).Non-invasive Assessment of Hemodynamic Response of Volume Expansion in Spontaneously Breathing Septic Shock Patients. *Biolife*. 6(2), 64-71. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7398974

Received: 1 March 2017; Accepted: 5 April 2018;
Published online: 13 May, 2018

Despite these recommendations, the reliability of CVP for guiding fluid resuscitation is controversial because of persistent inaccuracy when it is used as a

predictor of response to a volume bolus ^(4,5). There is now a large body of evidence to show that various dynamic parameters (both invasive and non-invasive) have a high sensitivity and specificity for predicting fluid responsiveness ⁽⁶⁾.

Cyclical changes in intra thoracic pressure induce changes in RAP, which alters venous return. In controlled ventilation, the IVC expands in inspiration and reduces in expiration. The absence of respiratory variation strongly suggests that the patient is not fluid responsive ⁽⁷⁾. In contrast, and similarly to LV outflow, large variations in IVC size with IPPV accurately predict fluid responsiveness. A diameter 'variability' cut-off value of more than 12% identifies responders ⁽⁸⁾.

IVC diameter variation has also been studied in spontaneously breathing patients without respiratory support; however, the evidence to support its use is weak and more studies needed to assess its rule in this type of patients ⁽⁹⁾.

Objective

To evaluate the extent to which, respiratory changes in IVC diameter, IVC-collapsibility index (IVC-CI) and left ventricular outflow tract VTI variations can be used to predict fluid responsiveness in septic shock spontaneously breathing not receiving positive mechanical ventilation patients in comparison to static parameters as central venous pressure.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Our study was a cross sectional randomized interventional study included thirty patients admitted to critical care department, Cairo university in Egypt diagnosed with acute circulatory failure secondary to septic shock collected during the period from January 2016 to June 2017 with permission from the institutional ethical committee.

A total of thirty spontaneously breathing septic shock patients enrolled in our study were subjected to fluid loading of crystalloids 10ml/kg infusion over 15 minutes. All patients were divided into two groups according to fluid responsiveness that defined by an increase in cardiac output 15% or more that measured by transthoracic echocardiography (TTE). Data were collected before and after fluid challenge including mean arterial pressure (MAP), heart rate (HR), central venous pressure (CVP) and saturation, inferior vena cava collapsibility index (IVCC) by TTE through subcostal window, long axis view and left ventricular outflow tract VTI by TTE through apical window, 5-chamber view to assess which parameter could reflect fluid status and responsiveness of the patient.

Inclusion Criteria:

All patients with acute circulatory failure secondary to sepsis according to the new definition and criteria of septic shock in surviving sepsis campaign 2017 (SSC)⁽¹⁰⁾ were included in the study.

Septic shock: sepsis with a vasopressor requirement to maintain a MAP \geq 65mmHg in spite of fluid resuscitation and serum lactate $>$ 2mmol/L.

Exclusion Criteria:

All Patients with positive pressure ventilation (either invasive or non-invasive positive pressure ventilation), pregnancy, severe aortic stenosis, cardiac arrhythmias, tricuspid insufficiency, congestive heart failure, active airway disease (concomitant diagnosis of acute exacerbation of asthma or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease) and difficult echocardiographic window were excluded from the study.

All patients enrolled in our study were subjected to :

- Full history and clinical examination.
- APACHE II scoring.
- Laboratory investigations including CBC, renal function tests, liver profile, coagulation profile and blood gases.
- Central line venous insertion to measure central venous pressure and saturation.
- Chest X-ray, ECG, Transthoracic echocardiography to assess ejection fraction, exclusion criteria, inferior vena cava collapsibility index and left ventricular outflow tract VTI variations before and after fluid challenge.

Statistical analysis

Data were collected, coded and entered using the statistical package SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version 24. Data was summarized using mean, standard deviation, median, minimum and maximum in quantitative data and using frequency (count) and relative frequency (percentage) for categorical data. Comparisons between quantitative variables were done using the non-parametric Mann-Whitney test. For comparison of serial measurements within each patient the non-parametric Wilcoxon signed rank test was used (Chan, 2003a). For comparing categorical data, Chi square (χ^2) test was performed. Exact test was used instead when the expected frequency is less than 5 (Chan, 2003b). Correlations between quantitative variables were done using Spearman correlation coefficient (Chan, 2003c). ROC curve was constructed with area under curve analysis performed to detect best cutoff value of different parameters for detection of response. P-values less than 0.05 were considered as statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our study enrolled a total of thirty patients; (46.6 %) were males and (53.3%) were females admitted to ICU with septic shock and were spontaneously breathing and were divided into two groups according to fluid responsiveness.

Demographic data were presented in table (1) and (2) showing that there was no significant statistical difference between both groups (p value more than 0.05) regarding age, gender, diabetes and hypertension.

Table-1. Study population demographic data.

	Responder			Non-responder			P
	Mean±SD	Median	Range	Mean±SD	Median	Range	
Age	61.6±16.2	66	29-85	56.6±12.6	57	35-80	0.3

Table-2. Comparison of measured hemodynamic static and dynamic parameters between both groups.

		Responder		Non-responder		P value
		Count	%	Count	%	
Gender	Male	6	33.3%	8	66.7%	0.073
	Female	12	66.7%	4	33.3%	
Diabetic	Yes	10	55.6%	5	41.7%	0.456
	No	8	44.4%	7	58.3%	
Hypertensive	Yes	11	55.6%	7	58.3%	0.880
	No	7	44.4%	5	41.7%	

A.Heart rate

There was no statistical significant difference between both groups in baseline heart rate and heart rate after volume expansion (p value more than 0.05) as presented in table (3).

pressure and mean arterial pressure after volume expansion (p value more than 0.05) as presented in table (4).

C.Central venous pressure (CVP) & Central venous saturation.

There was no statistical significant difference between responders and non-responders regarding mean baseline CVP, mean CVP after volume expansion and mean Δ CVP (p value more than 0.05) as presented in table (5).

Also there was no statistical significant difference between both groups in baseline oxygen saturation and after volume expansion from the central line as presented in table (6).

D.Left ventricular outflow tract (LVOT) VTI.

There was a statistically significant difference between responders and non-responders concerning mean baseline VTI before volume expansion (14.56 ± 4.06 in responders versus 19.00 ± 4.55 in non-responders with p value 0.004) with AUC:0.80, sensitivity of 83% and specificity of 83% and also in mean ΔVTI after volume expansion (29.21 ± 20.75 in responders versus 9.22 ± 6.14 in non-responders with p value less than 0.001) with AUC:0.92, sensitivity of 94 % and specificity of 83%.

There was no significant difference between both groups in mean VTI after volume expansion (18.68 ± 4.50 in responders versus 20.73 ± 5.04 in non-responders with p value :0.325, AUC:0.61, sensitivity of 50% and specificity of 83% as presented in table (7) and the ROC

Table-3. Comparison between both groups regarding heart rate before and after fluid challenge.

	Responder		Non-responder		P value
	Mean±SD	Median Range	Mean±SD	Median Range	
Heart rate (bpm) before	107.8±7.4	107.50 90-120	107.6±8.9	106.5 95-125	0.75
Heart rate (bpm) after VE	105.7±8	104.50 88-20	105.9±8.5	105.5 95-122	0.92

VE : Volume expansion

Table (4). Comparison between both groups in baseline MAP and after volume expansion.

	Responder		Non-responder		P value
	Mean±SD	Median Range	Mean±SD	Median Range	
Mean arterial pr (mmhg) before VE	42.2±8	43 27-53	43.2±4.7	43 35-53	0.8
Mean arterial pr (mmhg) after VE	53±7.9	53 40-67	49±5.3	48 42-59	0.15

pr :Pressure; VE :Volume expansion

B. Mean arterial blood pressure (MAP)

There was no statistical significant difference between both groups regarding baseline mean arterial

curve in figure (1) & (2)..

Table-5. Comparison between both groups in baseline CVP, after volume expansion and Δ CVP

	Responder			Non-responder			P value
	Mean \pm SD	Median	Range-	Mean \pm SD	Median	Range	
Central venous pr (mmhg) before VE	6 \pm 2.6	6	2-12	5.67 \pm 4.14	4.50	1-14	0.407
Central venous pr (mmhg) after VE	8.1 \pm 3.16	7.5	4-15	8.08 \pm 3.63	7.00	4-15	0.831
delta CVP	2.39 \pm 1.29	2.5	0-5	2.42 \pm .90	2.50	1-4	0.930

Table-6. Comparison between both groups in central venous oxygen saturation before and after volume expansion

	Responder			Non-responder			P value
	Mean \pm SD	Median	Range	Mean \pm SD	Median	Range	
Central venous saturation (%) before VE	50.8 \pm 7.6	50	41-64	53.7 \pm 7.3	53.50	41.00-70.00	0.285
Central venous saturation (%) after VE	55.4 \pm 5.8	55	47-69	56.7 \pm 7.2	54.50	46.00-72.00	0.692

Table-7. Comparison between both groups in LVOT VTI before and after volume expansion.

	Responder			Non-responder			P value
	Mean \pm SD	Median	Range	Mean \pm SD	Median	Range	
Velocity time integral (cm/s) before VE	14.6 \pm 4.06	13.85	8.40-27.00	19.00 \pm 4.55	18.25	12.20-27.00	.004
Velocity time integral (cm/s) after VE	18.68 \pm 4.50	17.70	10.70-29.00	20.73 \pm 5.04	18.85	13.80-28.50	.325
Velocity time integral (cm/s) delta VE	29.21 \pm 20.75	20.90	7.40-74.30	9.22 \pm 6.14	7.90	3.10-27.50	< 0.001

Table-8. Comparison between both groups regarding IVCC before and after volume expansion.

	Responder			Non-responder			P value
	Mean \pm SD	Median	Range	Mean \pm SD	Median	Range	
IVCC(%) before VE	50.05 \pm 14.82	51.85	19.00-66.60	43.78 \pm 18.09	48.05	17.00-80.10	.185
IVCC(%) after VE	29.08 \pm 10.21	34.00	8.30-39.80	24.30 \pm 12.74	23.65	9.00-46.00	.346
IVCC(%) delta VE	20.97 \pm 14.35	17.50	2.00-55.00	19.48 \pm 19.87	8.65	3.00-57.80	.518

E. Inferior vena cava collapsibility index (IVCC):

The results showing that there was no significant difference regarding all IVCC % readings between responders and non-responders spontaneously breathing septic shock patients as presented in [table \(8\)](#) with the ROC curve in [figure \(3\) &\(4\)](#). Baseline IVCC had AUC:0.64, sensitivity of 72% and specificity of 58%, IVCC after volume expansion had AUC:0.60, sensitivity of 66% and specificity of 75% and percentage of change of IVCC variations before and after fluid responsiveness had AUC:0.57, sensitivity of 83% and specificity of 58%.

In the current study responders had baseline central venous pressure (CVP) lower than non-responders (5 \pm 2.68 mmHg) vs. (5.67 \pm 4.14 mmHg) respectively , but this difference was not significant (P:0.407).

Similar to our results, *Cannesson M. et al.2009*, demonstrated failure of CVP to differentiate between responders and non-responders.CVP1 measurements were (11 \pm 5 mm Hg in responders vs. 11 \pm 4mm Hg in non-responders) (P : 0.74) ⁽¹¹⁾.

Also there is agreement between our study and that of *TakakoSasai. et al. 2014* Department of Anesthesiology, Okayama Red Cross Hospital, Okayama, Japan which

Figure-1. Baseline VTI (AUC:0.80 sensitivity of 83% specificity of 83%) VTI after volume expansion (AUC:0.61 sensitivity of 50% specificity of 83%).

Source of the Curve

- Velocity time integral (cm/s) 0
- Velocity time integral (cm/s) VE

Figure-3. Baseline IVCC (AUC:0.64 sensitivity of 72% specificity of 58%) IVCC after volume expansion (AUC:0.60 sensitivity of 66% specificity of 75%).

Source of the Curve

- IVCC(%) 0
- IVCC(%) VE

Figure-2. LVOT VTI percentage of change between before and after volume expansion (AUC:0.92 sensitivity of 94 % specificity of 83%).

Figure-4. Percentage of change of IVCC variations before and after fluid responsiveness (AUC:0.57 sensitivity of 83% specificity of 58%)

evaluate 40 adult patients with septic shock secondary to intra-abdominal infection who received active treatment and were monitored using transthoracic echocardiography (TTE) and CVP for 2 days after admission to our intensive care unit (ICU).who concluded that : CVP is not a reliable marker of left ventricular preload for fluid management during the initial phase of septic shock ⁽¹²⁾ .

In 2013, *Marik PE et al* perform an updated meta-analysis incorporating recent studies that investigated indices predictive of fluid responsiveness. From 191 articles screened, 43 studies were included for data extraction. The studies included human adult subjects, and included healthy controls (n = 1) and ICU (n = 22) and operating room (n = 20) patients. This systematic meta-analysis review demonstrated a very poor

relationship between CVP and blood volume as well as the inability of CVP/CVP change to predict the hemodynamic response to a fluid challenge and they recommended that CVP should not be used to make clinical decisions regarding fluid management⁽¹³⁾.

Regarding LVOT VTI, Our study found that there was a statistically significant difference between responders and non-responders concerning mean baseline VTI before volume expansion (14.56 ± 4.06 in responders versus 19.00 ± 4.55 in non-responders with p value 0.004) with sensitivity =83% and specificity=83% and also in mean Δ VTI after volume expansion (29.21 ± 20.75 in responders versus 9.22 ± 6.14 in non-responders with p value less than 0.001) with sensitivity of 94% and specificity of 83%.

There was no significant difference between both groups in mean VTI after volume expansion (18.68 ± 4.50 in responders versus 20.73 ± 5.04 in non-responders with p value: 0.325).

There is an agreement in our results and conclusion with *AstaMaciulene et al 2017* which is a prospective study that included 40 patients who underwent major abdominal surgery and had reduced arterial blood pressure. The echocardiography measurements were taken before and immediately after fluid challenge of 500 ml of crystalloids. Positive fluid responsiveness was defined by an increase in stroke volume (SV) of at least 15%⁽¹⁴⁾.

Results showed that variability of LVOT VTI during breathing cycle was significantly higher in responders compared to non-responders 14% (± 5.9) and 6.48% (± 12.9), respectively (p<0.001)⁽¹⁴⁾.

ROC analysis showed AUC 0.881 (95% CI 0.744–1.0, p<0.001), the best cut off value was 10% with 83.3% sensitivity and 85.7% specificity. So this study concluded that LVOT VTI variability of more than 10% in spontaneously breathing patients had the highest sensitivity and comparable specificity among the parameters used for identification of fluid responders⁽¹⁴⁾.

Also in another study showing the same significance, in *Ole Broch et al 2012* Ninety-two patients were studied before coronary artery surgery. Each patient was monitored with central venous pressure (CVP) and trans esophageal echocardiography. Responders were defined as those who increased their stroke volume index by greater than 15% (Δ SVI >15%) during passive leg raising⁽¹⁵⁾.

Central venous pressure showed no significant correlation with Δ SVI (r : -0.06, P : 0.58) in contrast to Δ VTI LVOT (r : 0.54, P < .0001) and The area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) predicting Δ SVI greater than 15% was found for Δ VTI LVOT (AUC: 0.74; P < .0001)⁽¹⁵⁾.

Regarding the role of inferior vena cava diameter and collapsibility index many studies were done among mechanically ventilated patients with acute circulatory failure and proved its significance to predict fluid responsiveness in this types of patient.

For example of these studies, *Feissel M. et al 2004* which studied the respiratory variations in inferior vena cava diameter as a guide to fluid therapy. The studies was conducted on 39 mechanically ventilated patients

with septic shock to investigate the effect of volume loading with 8mL/kg of 6% hydroxyethylstarsh on CO⁽⁷⁾. It concluded that $dIVC$ of $[(D_{max} - D_{min}) / 0.5 (D_{max} + D_{min})]$ or $[(D_{max} - D_{min})/D_{min}]$ can separate responders (increase in CO>15%) from non-responders with a sensitivity and specificity of around 90%⁽⁷⁾.

Zhongheng Zhang et al 2013 is a systematic meta-analysis was aimed at investigating the diagnostic accuracy of Δ IVC in predicting fluid responsiveness. A total of 8 studies involving 235 patients were eligible for analysis. Cutoff values of Δ IVC varied across studies, ranging from 12% to 40%. The pooled sensitivity and specificity in the overall population were 0.76 (95% confidence interval CI: 0.61–0.86) and 0.86 (95% CI: 0.69–0.95), respectively. The study founded that Δ IVC measured with point-of-care ultrasonography is of great value in predicting fluid responsiveness, particularly in patients on controlled mechanical ventilation and those resuscitated with colloids⁽¹⁶⁾.

Still the role of IVC diameter and collapsibility index in spontaneously breathing patients is of debate and many studies done with a different results. Our study assesses IVC collapsibility role for fluid responsiveness in spontaneously breathing patients.

Our study that included thirty patients admitted with signs of septic shock and were spontaneously breathing and the response to fluid challenge was defined as a 15% increase in cardiac output measured by trans thoracic echocardiography, showed that the area under the curve for baseline cIVC was 0.648 (95% CI : 0.43 – 0.85) with the best cutoff value 49.8% (sensitivity of 72.2% and specificity of 58.3%).

The area under the curve for cIVC after fluid challenge was 0.606 (95% CI : 0.37 – 0.83) with the best cutoff value 30% (sensitivity of 66.7% and specificity of 75%). The area under the curve for cIVC variation was 0.57 (95% CI : 0.33 – 0.80) with the best cutoff value 12.5% (sensitivity of 83.3% and specificity of 58.3%).

A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis, *Elliot et al .(2017)* showed agreement with our study results. Seventeen studies involving 533 patients were included, in whom 253 (47%) were fluid responders. The pooled sensitivity and specificity for a positive IVC ultrasound as a predictor of fluid responsiveness were 0.63 (95% confidence interval CI: 0.56–0.69) and 0.73 (95% CI: 0.67–0.78), respectively, with a pooled area under the receiver operating characteristic curve of 0.79 (standard error 0.05). This review concluded that Respiratory variation in IVC diameter has limited ability to predict fluid responsiveness, particularly in spontaneously ventilating patients. A negative test cannot be used to rule out fluid responsiveness⁽¹⁷⁾.

On the other hand there was a different results in another study *Lanspa et al. 2013*, Fourteen spontaneously breathing septic shock patients received 10-mL/kg volume expansion (VE) at their treating physician's discretion after initial resuscitation in the emergency department. They used transthoracic echocardiography to measure vena cava collapsibility index and aortic velocity variation before VE. Cardiac index was measured immediately before and after VE using transthoracic echocardiography.

Hemodynamic response was defined as an increase in cardiac index 15% or greater. Vena cava collapsibility index was predictive (area under the curve: 0.83, 0.92, respectively). Optimal thresholds were calculated: vena cava collapsibility index, 15% or greater (positive predictive value, 62%; negative predictive value, 100%; (P :0.03)⁽¹⁸⁾.

But there was a major study limitation which was a very small number of the patients included in this study⁽¹⁸⁾.

Also there is a disagreement with our results in *Preau et al.* (2017) study which was done on 90 non-intubated patients presented with sepsis-induced acute circulatory failure and considered for volume expansion induced by a 30-minute infusion of 500-mL gelatin 4%. They measured stroke volume index and collapsibility index of the inferior vena cava under a deep standardized inspiration using transthoracic echocardiography. Vena cava diameters were measured 15–20 mm caudal to the hepatic vein junction and recorded by bi dimensional imaging on a subcostal long-axis view. Standardized respiratory cycles consisted of a deep standardized inspiration followed by passive exhalation. The collapsibility index expressed in percentage equaled the ratio of the difference between end-expiratory and minimum-inspiratory diameter over the end-expiratory diameter. After volume expansion, a relevant ($\geq 10\%$) stroke volume index increase was recorded in 56% patients. In receiver operating characteristic analysis, the area under curve for that collapsibility index was 0.89 (95% CI, 0.82–0.97). When such index is superior or equal to 48%, fluid responsiveness is predicted with a sensitivity of 84% and a specificity of 90%⁽¹⁹⁾.

The difference may be due to the number of the patients, using other type of fluids, using a deep standardized inspiration and expiration which is difficult to be done in most of patients in our study due to hemodynamic instability⁽¹⁹⁾.

Limitation

- Small number of patients was a certainly serious drawback .
- Using different types, volumes and infusion rates of the fluids.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

In spite of high predictive value of IVCC to assess fluid responsiveness in mechanically ventilated patients, IVCC and CVP have a poor ability to predict fluid responsiveness in spontaneously breathing septic shock patient. In contrast, LVOT VTI has high predictive values in this type of patients.

We recommend increasing number of study population and studying other types of patients in need of fluid status management.

Conflicts of Interest

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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